

TMV WG

The purpose of the Group is to bring together the projects within the 5G-PPP that have common interest in the development of Test and Measurement methods, test cases, procedures and KPI validation. Moreover the Group aims at ensuring that projects are:

- working in a complimentary manner towards consistent goals
- exchanging ideas
- minimizing the duplication of effort, and
- leveraging and contributing to relevant standards such as ETSI NFV, ETSI MEC, ETSI ZSM, or 3GPP

Involved projects

	5g-vinni.eu
	5g-eve.eu
	5genesis.eu
	5gtango.eu
	5g-transformer.eu
	5g-picture-project.eu
	one5g.eu
	matilda-5g.eu

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5G-PPP WGs: www.5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-work-groups

Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation

5G PPP Working Group

5G PPP

Challenges

The 5G network is bringing new components, services, and technologies into the picture, including a heavy softwarization that is bridging the telco world with the IT one.

One of the biggest challenges is how to easily test, measure and demonstrate -for the wide range of new use cases and foreseeable conditions of deployments and scenarios- the performance KPIs of the new softwarized 5G network carrier-grade environments. New approaches and types of testing shall allow the fastest upgrade and deployment paces enabled by the software.

While the bridging of telco and IT changes how we test, and the type of tests, there is still a gap in doing End-to-End (E2E) and NFV/VNF characterizations and performance evaluation in the new 5G heterogeneous infrastructure (embracing generalized Virtualization, Network Slicing and Edge/Fog Computing). Test and Measurements (T&M) procedures, tools, and methodologies (testing, monitoring,

and analytics) need to be agreed upon, to ensure a proper functioning of the deployed networks.

The goal is to tightly integrate the T&M infrastructure as part of the service delivery and deployment system, orchestrating it across multiple, heterogeneous, and distributed cloud environments.

Research Areas of Interest

The Group considers the following research areas and technology domains:

- Testing KPI definition, KPI sources, collection procedures and analysis
- Testing frameworks (requirements, environment, scenarios, expectations, limitation) and tools
- Testing methodologies and procedures
- KPI validation methodologies
- Testing execution, monitoring, evaluation and reporting
- Common information models for 5G T&M

Another important topic is the use of and contribution towards open source projects such as OSM, OPNFV or ONAP and identification of relevant exploitation and dissemination targets.

Work Scope

- Demonstration of 5G KPIs (including 5G network E2E KPIs, 5G vertical service E2E KPIs)
- Enabler for trials / pilots (ICT-19)
- Support standardisation for addressing identified gaps with respect to the 5G PPP vision
- Leverage results from phase I and II in the scope of the WG
- Reproducibility properties of the experimentation
- Common and agreed methodology

The purpose of TMV is to bring together the 5G-PPP projects for common development and progression of topics related to T&M methods, test cases and procedures and KPI validation